

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20088798

PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION IN A DIGITAL SOCIETY

Abdurashid Mamasidikovich Mirzakhmedov^{1*}, Khurshid Abdurashidovich
Mirzakhmedov², Kamoldin Artikovich Elmirov³, Sevara Akramovna Pardaeva⁴

¹Doctor of Philosophy, Namangan State Technical University, Namangan, Republic of Uzbekistan. E-mail: mirzahmedov@mail.ru Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0635-4013>

²Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy in Sociology, Namangan State University, Namangan, Republic of Uzbekistan. E-mail: Devdas@mail.ru, Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6026-2262>

³Applicant, Department of Social Sciences, Namangan State Technical University, Namangan, Republic of Uzbekistan. E-mail: Sotsial.nauki@gmail.com

⁴Postgraduate Student, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University, Namangan, Republic of Uzbekistan. E-mail: Sotsial.nauki@gmail.com

Received: 06/04/2026
Accepted: 29/04/2026

Corresponding Author: Abdurashid Mamasidikovich Mirzakhmedov
(mirzahmedov@mail.ru)

ABSTRACT

This article examines the challenges of rethinking upbringing and education from the perspective of the ethno-confessional culture of the peoples of Central Asia, which reflects the tension between traditional and liberal values and the popularization of innovative pedagogical technologies from European countries. The relevance of this socio-cultural analysis stems from the substantiation of the ethno-confessional culture of Uzbek pedagogy, the revival of which fosters true meanings of spiritual and moral maturity, a righteous way of life and thought, and exemplary norms of behavior in the communication of the younger generation. The aim of this work is to rethink the social and collective upbringing of youth within the family of peoples of the region. This goal sets the objectives of a systemic, functional philosophical analysis of the crisis in the upbringing and education of young students drawn into internet addiction and the pathology of nomophobia. The materials for this article are drawn from universities in the Fergana Valley (Namangan and Fergana) and, for comparison, from students at Jizzakh State Pedagogical University. To ensure effectiveness, the study adopted a sociocultural approach, employing the following philosophical categories: general, specific, and particular, essence and content, system and function, and deductive and inductive methods. The authors see the resurgence of national systems and the functionality of traditional Eastern pedagogy in addressing the challenges of modern education. They place the responsibility for raising children within the family and in the school system, without which innovative European technology in schools in Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan loses its meaning, as well as the severe medical pathologies of internet addiction. The new generation of millennial youth finds itself caught between the virtual and real worlds, drawn into gambling with artificial intelligence and the "game without winning," falling into large financial debts. Thus, education becomes a matter of life or death, success or a global catastrophe.

KEYWORDS: Tradition And Innovation, Education, Teacher, Family and Marriage, Educational Model, Public Education, Mahalla, Internet Addiction, Nomophobia.

1. INTRODUCTION

The problem of education: Modern mass pedagogy is faced with a global threat to the ethno-confessional way of life and thought, as well as the norms of youth behavior in a post-industrial society. This has created an urgent need for a scientific rethinking of the education of the younger generation to ensure sustainable socio-cultural progress. Scientists have already discovered "...a contradiction between the existence of multiple approaches describing the essence and mechanisms of family education, ...which are the basis for the inheritance of culture and the transmission of experience from generation to generation" [8, p. 200]. The relevance of the problem of education is associated with the emergence of a "barricade" between adult children and their parents, the consequences of which are extremely dangerous for both the children's families and parents at the national, if not global, level. In the traditions of the peoples of the East, children are seen as a guarantee of a dignified life in old age and a guarantee of the continuation of their righteous way of life, so that their light will not be extinguished after their death, with a profound philosophical meaning to life. The digital system of society is alarming everyone, who have begun to realize that raising children is a shared concern not only for the family but also for society and the state, yet the issues of nationality and ethnicity have been forever forgotten. In this regard, it is absolutely true that "Education takes the person as he is, with all his national and individual characteristics—his body, soul, and mind—and above all addresses the person's character, and character is precisely the soil in which nationality is rooted" [14].

In traditional society, the family inherited all the material, spiritual, and moral values of the family and marriage. Parents protected their children from all threats posed by the environment. The mother nurtured them, raising them with her divine love, which became the foundation for the intellectual and moral socialization of the children's personality. The father demonstrated to the children the high moral character of a true man, a model of morality, honor, and the dignity of the head of the family. Thus, the family space served as a unique center for the formation and development of an individual's civic position based on the best ideals and models of ethno-confessional culture, the formation of a person based on the principles of religious and moral decency and the spiritual and moral beauty of human qualities. Global pedagogy is at an impasse, as educators face challenges arising from cultural

diversity and differences in values, as well as the complications of intergenerational relations in the era of transculturality [1; 15].

Digital society is transforming all spheres of society, bringing profound socio-cultural changes to family and marital life. The transition from the polynuclear family to the liberal nuclear family is reflected in the breakdown of social relationships between parents and children. The online electronic relationships of the information society have completely destroyed traditional norms of upbringing and parental control. Thus, the modern school is stalling and unable to provide a normal education, as the family has ceased to fulfill its nurturing function in accordance with the social mandate of society, "Domostroy." Thus, without school education, higher education is unable to professionalize young students. This raises the problem of the dialectical relationship between upbringing and education: without the former, there can be no latter. Another important factor in upbringing, as we see it, is the misconception that young people are being taught using European innovative technologies, which is far removed from the genetic ethno-confessional pedagogy of the peoples of Central Asia. This disconnects between upbringing and education leads to a breakdown in the collective responsibility of the family and school, and an overload of the entire educational process on the teacher. In this regard, we fully agree with Russian scholars that the slave labor of teachers is not compensated socially and financially, which "...forces school teachers to increase their workload at the expense of their physical and psycho-emotional recovery" [7, p. 687].

In Muslim society, the social role of the teacher is viewed as a key element in the entire educational process. When handing over his son for upbringing, a father pronounces the words, "The child's flesh is yours, but the bones are mine," denoting complete trust in the teacher's exemplary upbringing. As a mentor, the teacher not only imparts education—that is, a body of knowledge about life—but also shapes the student's personality based on the very best examples of socialization, ideas, and interests of Uzbek society. The teacher is the creator of great celebrities of the future, and student-teacher communication is an element of meditation on maturity, as students see their teacher as a model of the ideal person, a sage, and a great leader of science and knowledge.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In preparing this article, a sociocultural approach was used, focusing on inductive and deductive research methods. The study also utilized materials from foreign and domestic educational models, media reports from the Central Asian republics, and the results of sociological research conducted by the Department of Social Sciences, for which the authors are grateful. The research methods employed a dialectical approach, drawing on the social education models of Central Asian governments. Uzbekistan, for example, is implementing comprehensive reforms oriented toward innovative technologies from developed European countries, general and specific principles of national pedagogy, and is developing an axiological approach to the traditions and values of the Uzbek people. Thus, the sociocultural continuity method allows us to identify the principles of the formation and development of state youth policy, the evolution, and development trends of Uzbekistan's educational policy model.

3. SCIENTIFIC NOVELTY AND RESULTS

Eastern pedagogy established the ideas of collectivism and the principles of family labor education as the most important method for developing positive qualities in children, preparing them for household management, so that children could be true masters and mistresses of the family organization. In the patriarchal Uzbek family, they strove to raise and educate children in a spirit of physical health and the quality of hard work, honesty, and integrity in communal life. Thus, education obliged parents to feed their children only through honest labor, not allowing the consumption of stolen bread, which is emphasized to women from the beginning of pregnancy.

Since time immemorial, the Muslim community has considered the correct choice of bride for sons as the foundation of education. The highest good of a father for a son was the "choice of a mother of pure blood" from an elite family, with spiritual and moral authority, regardless of material and financial status in society. In this regard, the institution of matchmaking was formed by experienced elders possessing the diplomatic skills to conduct a thorough socio-cultural study of the similarities between the bride and groom's life together and their seven generations. Thus, the parameters for choosing a bride were to include the following qualities: a pious believer, of good family background, of normal financial status, and of attractive appearance. Such pre-wedding investigations between the parties guaranteed the stability of family relationships and

the strength of married life, which led to the establishment of a righteous lifestyle based on the principles of moral propriety for the newlyweds. Thus, Muslims considered the establishment and development of public education, which had the fateful character of a "Happy Family," to be the most serious event in education [11].

In Central Asian countries, communities live in "mahallas," a unique territorial center of collective life with an ethno-confessional way of life and culture. This ensures the transmission of social experiences from generation to generation, such as tolerance, philanthropy, moral kindness, and compassion, as well as a willingness to provide assistance to those in need, fostering shared collective honor and civic dignity. Thus, the collective guarantee of the mahalla manifests itself in the interaction of the "school, family, and mahalla" format as a systematic and functional continuity of pedagogical influence on the younger generation, in which the family assumes responsibility for upbringing, and the school, along with the mahalla, promotes morality in children's behavior. Thus, the mahalla acts as a non-governmental system for educating children and their parents, in short, a local primary school overseeing the inculcation of universal human values: interethnic harmony, respect for elders, care for the young, collective mutual assistance, respect for national traditions and values, and the promotion of family and marriage strength. This idea can be supported by research by renowned educational psychologists [2].

The upbringing of a young Uzbek is based on a strict hierarchy of respect and authority in the family and society, in which the father leads as the head of the family, followed by the mother, who occupies a place of honor for children according to their ages. However, within the family, the mother's authority and honor are supreme, along with girls, as Islam places women above all men, with laws such as "Heaven is under the feet of mothers," "If a mother sits on her son's shoulders, then a sister sits on her brother's head," and many other teachings on women's care in the family and marriage. The Quran obliges children to pray to Allah with the words: "And bow to them both the wing of humility out of mercy, and say: 'My Lord! 'Have mercy on them, as they raised me as a child,' because my parents bestowed upon me all they had, cared for me, and sacrificed themselves [6]. Islamic pedagogical doctrine establishes theories of education based on the following requirements: "Children under three years of age should be treated as a ruler, from three to sixteen as slaves, and from seventeen as a friend,"

which establishes an unwritten law of children's complete submission to their parents, respect, and assistance in all things in old age. We are inclined to believe that education is based on the idea of fear of Allah and the second place of the father, as sacred values of existence. Fear of Allah shapes high spirituality and norms of moral behavior in an individual [11, p. 22].

Udmurt scholars associate the challenges of improving the quality of education with the personality of the teacher, the teacher-educator, as "...a person with a big heart, intelligent, searching, constantly working on themselves and motivating their students. We believe that it is impossible to work as a teacher and not love their students...teachers are those who sow kindness, eternity, and wisdom" [16, p. 129]. We agree with the authors that the modern teacher is burdened with the impossible responsibilities of the information society, and that their working hours are difficult to establish, since students can turn in homework at any time outside of the teacher's working hours. Thus, students are equipped with the latest ICT advances, and their awareness creates a complex educational process; that is, armed sheep are more dangerous than armed wolves. In this regard, it is worth noting the increased workload, which requires high physical and intellectual performance on the part of the teacher. Another important issue in parenting concerns gender equality in the family, where fathers lack confidence in addressing issues of spiritual and moral development, whether it's curing children of internet addiction, prohibiting them from using mobile phones, or much else. These problems are growing, compounded by the feminization of the family as governments adopt policies to protect children's rights, banning corporal punishment. In single-parent families, the situation is even worse, with chaotic parenting. Thus, the modern digital family has ceased to be the most important unit for socializing individuals based on the best traditions and values of children's behavior. In a digital society, not only the family but also the school prioritizes children's material well-being over their spiritual, moral, and intellectual development. This is why there is a need to define the goals and objectives of parenting: to raise a fighter or an artist, a tractor driver or an engineer, and most importantly, a worthy citizen of the country.

4. DISCUSSION

The problem of modern education in post-industrial countries can be divided into two areas. First, China and Japan, with favorable conditions and

heightened demands for children's physical and intellectual development. However, in European countries, the ratings of upbringing and education are declining, with amorality, depravity of spiritual and moral values, a devaluation of church ideology, and family secularism flourishing [10, p. 48]. Global digital culture in public life impacts families and marriages, negatively affecting parental influence on the development of a child's personality, children's mastery of school curricula, and a weakening of behavioral controls in the school educational process. Against the backdrop of the liberalization of the educational process with innovative technologies, teacher authority is rapidly declining, with demanding teachers being physically punished by parents or relatives if they are not dismissed from their positions, despite the law stipulating that "the rights, honor, dignity, and professional reputation of a teacher are protected by the state," which is usually decided in favor of the student [5]. We have observed "emotional burnout syndrome," with the teaching profession entering a high-risk category. Computerization burdens teachers with enormous demands on their upbringing and education from parents and school administrations, without providing them with a bucket of "kefir" for working in hazardous conditions, which is raising alarm bells in psychology [2, p. 84]. According to sociologists, "...in 2020, 75% of teachers surveyed in Russia had pronounced symptoms of burnout, and 38% were in the acute phase, when burnout significantly impacts their quality of life and ability to work" [4, p. 61].

Education has a purely national character, with socio-cultural roots in every nation, which is why many peoples of the world have departed from their cultural codes of national standards and traditional moral models. This topic was relevant for the West, which noted the decline of the spiritual and moral life of the peoples of Central Asia [17]. The reason for the spiritual and moral "decline" of family and marital life, the relationship between child and female crime, according to A.S. Makarenko, is "...the social conditions surrounding the adult, the environment, ... the goals of which will be: discipline, efficiency, honesty, political consciousness. Heroic measures must be taken to satisfy this minimum" [8, p. 75]. In reality, in the modern information society, children have ceased to engage in useful work, without which it is impossible to form a true citizen of the country; children do not receive lessons in thrift in the family, and cannot value the ruble of their labor. Russian scholars already acknowledge that "...the problem of finding effective mechanisms for educating the younger generation and its social

integration is confronting the discrepancy between the youth socialization model and the changing conditions of social relations, which are affected by 'new wars' and escalating social conflicts" [13, p. 67].

Kazakh scholars have grouped the principles of education into:

- education is determined by the culture of society;

- education and training are two interpenetrating, interdependent processes with the decisive role of education;

- the effectiveness of education is determined by a person's activity and their involvement in self-education;

- the effectiveness and efficiency of education depend on the harmonious connection of all structural elements involved in the educational process: goals, content, forms, methods, and means appropriate to the child and teacher" [12, p. 449]. However, we favor two patterns of education, the content of which is divided into universal and national norms and principles of culture. This implies the social spirituality of culture, established through a philosophical way of life and a style of thinking based on the individual's social position and worldview [9, p. 24]. The complication of education problems should be considered in the need to reform the social structure and forms of production based on the digitalization of society, which equips young people with the latest advances in ICT. With the globalization of information technology tightly integrated with a wide youth audience, young people are becoming internet dependent, i.e., child addiction is observed. Sociological analyses have shown a general pattern: in families that adhere to the norms of tradition and values, parental authority "ensures, protects, bears responsibility, and makes key decisions related to family life. Children's needs are taken into account, but do not prevail over the needs of their parents" [8, p. 211]. In this way, children develop respect for their parents, who take responsibility for the material and spiritual well-being of the family, which is the basis of education.

5. CONCLUSION

In Uzbekistan, the mahalla developed as a social institution of civil society, serving as a unique form of organizing a collective way of life, the initial unit for educating the younger generation based on the best traditions and values of the Uzbek people, with the principle of "One for all, all for one." The mahalla was a unique community of people living by the unity of national and universal spiritual values, and a code of spiritual and moral decency. Thus, the

mahalla can be considered an important factor in personality development, grounded in national traditions and taking into account the harmony of the most positive qualities of upbringing within the individual. Uzbekistan's youth policy strategy is based on a clear system of principles: stable families and lasting marriages, the socio-cultural protection of young people by the family, viewing the family and marriage as the primary school of society, where everyone's accumulated experience of the social structure of family life and marriage is transmitted.

Education, at its core, is a parental social duty to society to prepare children for a dignified collective life, obedience to ethno-confessional traditions, and cultural values. The political system assigns educational responsibilities to families, and educational responsibilities to schools. Civil institutions assist them in shaping individuals in accordance with society's ideals. In this context, society defines the goals of education: to raise a fighter or an artist, a tractor driver or an engineer – the most important of all, a worthy citizen of the country. The problem lies in the correct methodology of young Greeks or Uzbeks, Englishmen and Americans, which has become disconnected from its ethno-confessional roots, and which has been overtaken by mass pedagogy and modern educational science. Today's youth is losing their ethno-confessional identity, with the system of qualities of "mass culture," the popularization of its views, beliefs, worldviews, attitudes, and behaviors, making it impossible to train a "social animal".

We tend to think that no nation in the world encourages childlessness or living for one's own pleasure. Islam, however, proclaims children to be the flowers of paradise. In the family, mothers are entrusted with bringing light to the child, nurturing and raising them with mother's milk and love, for which all their sins are washed away. Islam places great importance on raising children; parents deserve paradise solely for the high moral standards of their children's behavior, for raising them to be worthy individuals who contribute to society. In family upbringing, the focus is on fidelity to the ideals of Islam, based on respect for parents, the priority of love, and respect for mothers. Children must show due respect to their parents and reciprocate their love and gratitude for their upbringing. Raising their voices or being tactless toward their children is strictly forbidden to parents, as it is a grave sin. Islam views upbringing as an ideal of parents, showing a model of respect and love for children. Everything in the family is transformed into a family for the children, through the selfless care they show for their

parents.

Education as a social, dialectical phenomenon requires new approaches and solutions appropriate to each people, nation, and even each child. Traditional formulations and understandings fail to produce the expected results in a modern world with a global information field and audience. The global nature of modern pedagogy compels everyone to collectivize creative forces and opportunities, which is the duty of progressive humanity. The tasks of education beseech us to proclaim the slogan: "Educators of all countries, unite!" for the celebration

of high spiritual morality.

Parenting is a simple matter, but re-education is a delicate and sensitive one, if possible. Nevertheless, the challenge of re-educating a population transitioning to a digitalized society has emerged globally. Against the backdrop of gender equality and children's rights in Muslim countries, norms and traditions of education are at odds. It's worth emphasizing the even more complex problem of "intellectual myopia" due to artificial intelligence: from calculators to the internet in the education system. The question remains: "What to do?"

Author Contributions: For research articles with multiple authors, please provide a brief paragraph indicating the individual authors' contributions. The following language should be used: Introduction, Sevara Pardaeva; Materials and Methods, Kamoldin Elmirov; Scientific Novelty And Results, Khurshid Mirzakhmedov; Discussion and Conclusion, Abdurashid Mirzakhmedov

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: This article was prepared with the support of grant IL-9124104620-R1 Agency for Innovative Development under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the scientific project of Namangan State Technical University, for which the authors express their gratitude to the management of the agency.

REFERENCES

- Anderstaf S., Lecusay R., Nilsson M. (2021) Sometimes we have to clash: how preschool teachers in Sweden engage with dilemmas arising from cultural diversity and value differences. *Intercultural education*. 32 (3), 296-310.
- Christiansen B. (2020) *Global Applications of Multigenerational Management and Leadership in the Transcultural Era*. Global Research Society, LLC, USA. 328 p.
- Egoryshev S.V. (2023) Emotional burnout of teachers as a factor in reducing the effectiveness of their professional activity. *RUDN University Bulletin. Series: Sociology*. 23(1), 61-73.
- Krachkovsky I. Yu. (1963). *Quran*. -M.: Publishing House of Eastern Literature. 191 p.
- Kudinov S.I. Sedova V. (2023) Emotional Burnout in School Teachers with Different Self-Attitude Indicators. *SibScript*, , 25(5): 687-695
- Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Status of a Teacher" dated February 1, 2024, ZRU-901. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6786403>
- Lykova I. A., Mayer A. A. (2022) Systematization of Family Education Traditions: A Social and Pedagogical Classifier. *Science for Education Today*. 12(5), 200-224.
- Makarenko A. S. (1990) *On Education / compiled by V. S. Khelemendik*. - Moscow: Politizdat, 415 p.
- Mirzahmedov A. Mirzahmedov H. (2022) The problem of religion in the modern system of secular education. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*. 14 (05), 48-52.
- Mirzakhmedov A. Elmirov K. (2021) *Philosophy of Education*. Alma Mater. *Bulletin of Universities*. 4, 24-31.
- Muhammad Sadyk M. Yu. (2019) *Happy Family*. - Tashkent: Hilol nashr. 608 p.
- Shamseeva G. Kh., Akhmetzyanova G. R., Kuvanova I. Kh. (2022) On the role of a modern teacher in the educational process: sociological analysis. *Bulletin of Economics, Law and Sociology*. 4, 129-132.
- Sikhynbaeva Zh.S., Kuramysova A., Otarbaeva S., Ashimov T.K., Zhunisov G.B. (2016) The educational process is an integral part of the holistic pedagogical process. *International Journal of Experimental Education*. 12(3), 449-450.
- Smirnov V. A., Gruzdev V. V., (2025) Smirnova L. N. Model of social education of youth of the Russian Orthodox Church: axiology, methodology, social technologies // *Science for Education Today*. 15(1), 66-89.
- Spengler O. (1998) *The Decline of the West*. -Rostov n/D: Phoenix, 640 p
- Ushinsky K. (1857) On nationality in public education // *Magazine for education*. 7(8). <https://ru.wikisource.org/wiki/>
- Vachkov I.V., Savenkova M.A. (2019) Features of emotional burnout of teachers with different types of coping

strategies. Bulletin of Moscow City Pedagogical Univ. Series "Pedagogy and Psychology". 3, 84-95.

Volobueva L.M., Zvereva O.L., Avilova E.A. (2025) Updating the domestic scientific heritage as a condition for developing the competencies of modern preschool teachers. Pedagogical education and science. 1, 142-149.